

THE INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE ON THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY AND VISCOSITY OF AQUEOUS MERCURIC CHLORIDE.

BY SRIDHAR SARVOTTAM JOSHI AND DUSHYANT NARASINGASA SOLANKI.

Conductivities and viscosities of aqueous mercuric chloride of $0.125M$ – $0.00939M$ conc. have been determined within 15° to 40° . The conductivity is extremely low almost equal to that of non-electrolyte. It increases, however, more rapidly with temperature (about 3.8 to 6.2%) than is observed in aqueous solution of strong electrolytes. It is considered that the ionisation of $HgCl_2$ involves, besides those derived from its binary dissociation, other and more complex ions. This might explain in part the observed discrepancy from Kraus and Bray's formula. Authors' data for the influence of temperature on conductivity are in agreement with Kohlrausch's equation. The variation of viscosity with concentration and temperature can adequately be expressed by Berl and Umstätter and Karrer's equations. The temperature coefficients of viscosity of $HgCl_2$ solutions are almost equal to those of the pure solvent, water. It is also seen that the temperature coefficient of viscosity of solvent (water) remains unaltered in spite of the varying concentration of $HgCl_2$ present in the system. Authors' data for the influence of temperature on viscosity are in agreement with Bousfield and Lowry's equation.

The very low conducting nature of mercuric chloride, both in the solid and molten state was, perhaps, first established by Faraday (*Phil. Trans.*, 1834, **124**, 77; 1838, **128**, 83), Clark (*Phil. Mag.*, 1885, *v*, **20**, 37), Hampe (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1887, **11**, 904), Fritsch (*Ann. phys. chim.*, 1897, *ii*, **60**, 308), Foot and Martin (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1909, **41**, 454) and others. Cold saturated solution of mercuric chloride was found by Hampe (*loc. cit.*), Faraday (*loc. cit.*) and Morse (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, **41**, 709) to be a poor conductor of electricity. The conductivity of aqueous solutions has been measured by Grotrian (*Wied. Ann.*, 1883, **18**, 192), Fitzpatrick (*Phil. Mag.*, 1887, *v*, **24**, 384), Ley and Kissel (*Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 1358), Jones and Oata (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1899, **22**, 12), Kahlenberg (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1901, **5**, 339) and Holdermann (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1905, **243**, 616). Ley (*Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 2195; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, **30**, 247) demonstrated that the conductivities are rather less with plain than with platinised platinum electrodes. Arctowsky (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1885, **9**, 188) found that the electrical conductivity of aqueous solution increases

perceptibly on standing, presumably because of hydrolysis and the corresponding formation of hydrochloric acid. That the dissociation constant for HgCl_2 is of a very low order and that the dissociation takes place in stages has been demonstrated by the work of Luther (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, **36**, 402; 1904, **47**, 107) and Sherill (*ibid.*, 1903, **43**, 734; 1904, **47**, 103). Kohlrausch and Nippoldt (*Ann. phys. chim.*, *ii*, **26**, 161) and Kohlrausch and Grotrian (*Dingl. Polyt. J.*, **114**, 337) carried out investigations on the temperature coefficients of conductivity of several electrolytes in aqueous solutions. Their results were further confirmed by Schaller (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, **25**, 497). Eversheim (*Ann. Physik*, 1902, *iv*, **8**, 539) studied the electrical conductivity of HgCl_2 in organic solvents, ethyl chloride and ethyl ether, at different temperatures and also measured the dielectric constant at different temperatures. Rasch and Hinrichsen (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1908, **14**, 41) from conductivity measurements at different temperatures arrived at the expression

$$\frac{d \log K}{dT} = - \frac{q}{RT^2},$$

connecting K , the conductivity of an electrolyte and temperature. Noyes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 335) from the study of the effect of temperature on the conductivity and ionisation of acids, bases and salts came to a definite conclusion that in general the ionisation decreases steadily with rise of temperature in the case of every substance investigated by the authors; the effect of temperature on ionisation of salts is comparable with its effects on the dielectric constant of water. Bousfield and Lowry (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1902, **A71**, 42) concluded that the two factors which determine the form of temperature-conductivity curves are: (a) the increase of η and decrease of ionic mobilities with falling temperature; (b) the decrease of ionisation with rising temperature; and the temperature coefficient of conductivity will be positive or negative according as one or the other of these two factors predominates. The authors also showed that the viscosity-temperature relation can be expressed by the formula

$$\eta_{18} = \eta_t [1 + \alpha(t - 18) + \beta(t - 18)^2]$$

analogous to Kohlrausch's formula (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1903, **A71**, 338) for conductivity,

$$K_t = K_{18} [1 + \alpha(t - 18) + \beta(t - 18)^2]$$

the coefficients α , and β , being nearly the same in both the formulae when applied to water. Jones and West (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1905, **34**, 357; 1909, **42**, 520) showed that the percentage dissociation and percentage temperature coefficients of conductivity decrease as the temperature is raised. Their results are in close harmony with the observations of Ramsay and Shields (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, **63**, 1089) and Dutoit and Astons hypothesis. The data of Vonwiller (*Phil. Mag.*, 1904, *vi*, 7, 655) also lead to the same conclusions. Jones (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1906, **35**, 445) further pointed out the bearing of hydrates on temporary coefficients of conductivity in aqueous solutions. The relation between the nature and properties of solvent and its ionising capacity, electrical conductivity and its temperature coefficients in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions of salts have been investigated by many workers*.

From the viscosity measurements of a large number of electrolytes Taylor and Moore (*Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1908, **27**, 461), Getman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 721; *J. chim. phys.*, 1907, **5**, 344) and others have shown that there are two types of salts, one type showing 'positive' viscosity effect and the other type showing 'negative' viscosity effect and that the viscosity of salt solutions cannot be regarded as simply an additive property. They further showed that the cations in opposition to undissociated molecules and anions, tended to diminish the viscosity of water and in general, this lowering effect of the cation was shown to be proportional to its atomic volume by Jones and Veazey (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1907, **37**, 405); anions and non-dissociated molecules, on the other hand, were shown to increase the viscosity of the solvent. The molecular complex formation also was shown to affect the viscosity to a remarkable extent. Tamman and Rabe (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, **162**, 17) studied the effect of temperature on the surface tension of electrolytic solutions. A general formula of the type

$$\eta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/\eta = 1 - 0.02013\sqrt{C} - 0.20087C$$

has been deduced by Jones and Dole (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950), the coefficient \sqrt{C} is negative for strong electrolytes and zero for non-electrolytes and the coefficient C is negative for those salts which increase the viscosity of water at all concentrations. Falkenhagen and

* Giulio Coffetti (*Gazzetta*, 1903, **33**, 53), White and Jones (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1909, **42**, 520), Inclin (*Annal. Fis. Quim.*, 1906, **4**, 94), Kohlrausch and Maltby (*Wiss. Abhandl. Phys. Tec. Reich-Sanstalt*, 1900, **3**, 155) and others.

Dole (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **B6**, 159) proposed a square root law for the viscosity of strong electrolytes, $\eta_c = \eta_o(1 + A\sqrt{C})$ where C is the normality of the solution, η_c and η_o , the viscosity coefficients of the solution and solvent respectively, and A is a constant. Berl and Umstätter and Karrer (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **152**, 284) proposed equations, to express the variation of viscosity with temperature and concentration,

$$\log \eta = \frac{B}{T} - A, \quad \log \eta = KC,$$

where C is volume concentration, T , the absolute temperature K , A , and B are constants. The present work on aqueous HgCl_2 was suggested by observation of its high coagulative power (in contrast with low ionisation and conductivity) and other anomalous behaviour as a coagulant (*cf.*, Joshi and Kulkarni, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 439; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1937, **14**, 103; Joshi and Ram Das, *ibid.*, 1937, **14**, 167). Joshi and Krishna Rao (results to be published] have found that HgCl_2 has an abnormally high adsorbability towards animal charcoal and colloid As_2S_3 . Similar deviations from normality as revealed by conductivity measurements were also noticed in its behaviour towards aqueous benzoic acid (Joshi and Solanki, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 323). The very considerable amount of data on the conductance of a large number of substances obtained by Kohrausch (*loc. cit.*), Melcher and Cooper (*loc. cit.*), Bousefield and Lowry (*loc. cit.*), and Jones (*loc. cit.*) has served to show their marked utility together with those for the viscosity of the medium at different temperatures, in the classification of the solutes in respect of their molecular and ionising behaviour. It was of interest therefore, to study the behaviour of HgCl_2 in the light of the above theories.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Conductivity determinations of aqueous mercuric chloride (Merck's guaranteed extra pure) were made at 15°, 20°, 25°, 30°, 35°, and 40°. The containers were all of high resistance Jena glass. The conductivity cell used was of pyrex glass with the platinum electrodes, each of 1 sq. cm. area, fixed vertically, the inter-electrode distance being 1.2 cm. The bridge employed for the determination of electrolytic resistances was Pye's modified Post Office Box of dial resistance type; a small Kohrausch coil

was used as an A. C. generator. The conductivity water used for experiments was prepared by distilling twice distilled water in Hartley's conductivity still and collecting only the middle fraction, the first and the last fractions being rejected. This stock of water which was used for making the various solutions was tested for its constancy of conductivity. The cell constant was determined every now and then by using freshly prepared $N/50$ -KCl solution at $25 \pm 0.05^\circ$. The same cell constant was used for calculating the conductivity at the remaining temperatures, ranging from 15° to 40° , the variation of the cell constant with temperature especially for 10° to 15° differences being negligible. The electrodes with freshly platinised surfaces were always kept immersed in conductivity water after the completion of an experiment.

Fresh solution of $HgCl_2$ was prepared at every temperature ; dilution was made to the exact mark at the respective temperature to avoid the volume changes due to changes in densities. Throughout the experimental procedure the method of successive dilution was adopted, the observations being recorded in the order of their determination *i.e.*, from concentrated to dilute solutions.

The viscosity determinations of these solutions were also made at different temperatures 15° , 20° , 25° , 30° , 35° , and 40° by adopting Scarpa's method (*Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271) modified by Farrow (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912 101, 347) and later on further modified by Joshi and Nanjappa (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 133 *et seq.*). Extreme precautions were taken specially in cleaning the viscometer and in maintaining the temperature control within 0.05° .

In Tables I to IV are recorded the values for the conductivities of mercuric chloride.

Tables VII to X record the values for the temperature coefficients of conductivity for different concentrations and for different temperature ranges.

Table XI gives in absolute units the viscosities at different temperatures together with their logarithms.

In Tables XII-XV are recorded the values for the temperature coefficients of viscosity for different concentrations and for different temperature ranges.

In the following tables C stands for concentration in moles per litre, R for resistance in ohms, κ for specific conductivity in mhos, η for viscosity of solution, η_0 for viscosity of water and Λ for molecular conductivity corrected for viscosity in mhos.

TABLE I.

Conductivity of HgCl₂ solutions.

Temp. = $15^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$. Cell constant = 0.3776. Sp. conductivity of water = 1.035×10^{-6} mhos.

C .	R .	κ .	η/η_0 .	Λ .	CA .	$1/\Lambda$.	Log (CA).	Log [CA^2]
0.125	4267	0.00008744	1.018	0.7124	0.08904	1.404	$\bar{2}.9496$	$\bar{2}.8023$
0.09375	4952	0.00007520	1.014	0.8128	0.07619	1.230	$\bar{2}.8819$	$\bar{2}.7919$
0.07031	5687	0.00006536	1.010	0.9392	0.06606	1.064	$\bar{2}.8199$	$\bar{2}.7027$
0.0527	6425	0.00005773	1.009	1.1054	0.05825	0.9046	$\bar{2}.7653$	$\bar{2}.8088$
0.03955	7185	0.00005151	1.007	1.3114	0.05186	0.7626	$\bar{2}.7148$	$\bar{2}.8325$
0.02966	8065	0.00004577	1.003	1.5482	0.04591	0.6462	$\bar{2}.6619$	$\bar{2}.8516$
0.02225	9105	0.00004044	1.003	1.8232	0.04057	0.5486	$\bar{2}.6082$	$\bar{2}.8690$
0.01669	10095	0.00003637	1.004	2.1880	0.03653	0.4569	$\bar{2}.5626$	$\bar{2}.9027$
0.01251	11165	0.00003279	1.001	2.622	0.03279	0.3815	$\bar{2}.5158$	$\bar{2}.9344$
0.00939	12355	0.00002952	1.001	3.146	0.02954	0.3179	$\bar{2}.4704$	$\bar{2}.9681$

TABLE II.

Temp. = $20 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Cell constant = 0.3776. Sp. conductivity of water = 1.035×10^{-6} mhos.

C .	R .	κ .	η/η_0 .	Λ .	CA .	$1/\Lambda$.	Log [CA].	Log [CA^2].
0.125	3464	0.0001080	1.015	0.8766	0.1096	1.141	1.0397	$\bar{2}.9825$
0.09375	3992	0.00009353	1.011	1.0086	0.09452	0.9917	$\bar{2}.9755$	$\bar{2}.9791$
0.07031	4518	0.00008251	1.007	1.1826	0.08318	0.8455	$\bar{2}.9200$	$\bar{2}.9949$
0.0527	5165	0.00007207	1.006	1.3748	0.07246	0.7273	$\bar{2}.8601$	$\bar{2}.9984$
0.03955	5783	0.00006425	1.000	1.6246	0.06424	0.6156	$\bar{2}.8078$	$\bar{1}.0185$
0.02966	6555	0.00005656	1.001	1.9078	0.05659	0.5241	$\bar{2}.7528$	$\bar{1}.0334$
0.02225	7313	0.00005059	0.9993	2.272	0.05056	0.4401	$\bar{2}.7038$	$\bar{1}.0602$
0.01669	8153	0.00004526	1.001	2.716	0.04533	0.3682	$\bar{2}.6564$	$\bar{1}.0903$
0.01251	9132	0.00004030	0.9993	3.218	0.04025	0.3108	$\bar{2}.6048$	$\bar{1}.1124$
0.00939	9893	0.00003713	1.001	3.958	0.03717	0.2526	$\bar{2}.5702$	$\bar{1}.1677$

TABLE III.

Temp. = $25 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Cell constant = 0.3776. Sp. conductivity of water = 1.11×10^{-6} mhos.

C.	R.	κ .	η/η_0 .	Λ .	CA.	1/A.	Log [CA]	Log [CA ²]
0.125	2837	0.0001319	1.017	1.0736	0.1342	0.9313	$\bar{1}.1278$	$\bar{1}.1587$
0.09375	3283	0.0001139	1.015	1.2332	0.1155	0.8112	$\bar{1}.0628$	$\bar{1}.1537$
0.07031	3786	0.00009860	1.011	1.4182	0.09970	0.7053	$\bar{2}.9987$	$\bar{1}.1503$
0.0527	4295	0.00008678	1.008	1.6602	0.08748	0.6024	$\bar{2}.9419$	$\bar{1}.1620$
0.03955	4786	0.00007779	1.007	1.9786	0.07807	0.5065	$\bar{2}.8925$	$\bar{1}.1879$
0.02966	5364	0.00006927	1.005	2.346	0.06958	0.4263	$\bar{2}.8425$	$\bar{1}.2128$
0.02225	5983	0.00006200	1.003	2.794	0.06218	0.3580	$\bar{2}.7936$	$\bar{1}.2398$
0.01669	6766	0.00005470	1.002	3.286	0.05486	0.3043	$\bar{2}.7392$	$\bar{1}.2559$
0.01251	7477	0.00004939	1.002	3.954	0.04945	0.2529	$\bar{2}.6942$	$\bar{1}.2912$
0.00939	8314	0.00004430	1.001	4.722	0.04434	0.2117	$\bar{2}.6468$	$\bar{1}.3209$

TABLE IV.

Temp. = $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$ Cell constant = 0.3776. Sp. conductivity of water = 1.16×10^{-6} mhos.

C.	R.	κ	$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$.	Λ .	CA.	1/A.	Log [CA]	Log [CA ²]
0.125	2370	0.0001581	1.017	1.2856	0.1607	0.7776	$\bar{1}.2061$	$\bar{1}.3153$
0.09375	2723	0.0001375	1.013	1.4846	0.1392	0.6735	$\bar{1}.1436$	$\bar{1}.3153$
0.07031	3113	0.0001201	1.009	1.7232	0.1212	0.5805	$\bar{1}.0833$	$\bar{1}.3195$
0.0527	3552	0.0001051	1.008	2.010	0.1059	0.4975	$\bar{1}.0250$	$\bar{1}.3282$
0.03955	3915	0.00009528	1.006	2.424	0.09585	0.4126	$\bar{2}.9816$	$\bar{1}.3661$
0.02966	4422	0.00008422	1.002	2.844	0.08435	0.3517	$\bar{2}.9261$	$\bar{1}.3800$
0.02225	4937	0.00007532	1.001	3.388	0.07539	0.2952	$\bar{2}.8773$	$\bar{1}.4072$
0.01669	5498	0.00006751	1.001	4.050	0.06745	0.2469	$\bar{2}.8290$	$\bar{1}.4365$
0.01251	6038	0.00006137	1.001	4.912	0.06145	0.2035	$\bar{2}.7885$	$\bar{1}.4798$
0.00939	6723	0.00005499	1.000	5.856	0.05499	0.1708	$\bar{2}.7403$	$\bar{1}.5079$

TABLE V.

Temp. = $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Cell constant = 0.3776 . Sp. conductivity of water = 1.25×10^{-6} mhos.

C.	R.	κ .	$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$.	Λ .	CA.	$1/\Lambda$.	Log [CA].	Log [CA ²].
0.125	1903	0.0001881	1.015	1.5280	0.1909	0.6546	$\bar{1}.2809$	$\bar{1}.4649$
0.09375	2282	0.0001642	1.010	1.7694	0.1659	0.5652	$\bar{1}.2197$	$\bar{1}.4675$
0.07031	2646	0.0001414	1.007	2.026	0.1425	0.4935	$\bar{1}.1538$	$\bar{1}.4605$
0.0527	2956	0.0001264	1.006	2.432	0.1224	0.4111	$\bar{1}.0878$	$\bar{1}.4738$
0.03955	3361	0.0001111	1.008	2.830	0.1119	0.3534	$\bar{1}.0489$	$\bar{1}.5007$
0.02966	3803	0.00009802	1.006	3.324	0.09858	0.3009	$\bar{2}.9938$	$\bar{1}.5154$
0.02225	4174	0.00008918	1.002	4.016	0.08935	0.2491	$\bar{2}.9511$	$\bar{1}.5548$
0.01669	4681	0.00007941	1.003	4.772	0.07966	0.2095	$\bar{2}.9012$	$\bar{1}.5799$
0.01251	5143	0.00007214	1.001	5.772	0.07221	0.1732	$\bar{2}.8586$	$\bar{1}.6200$
0.00939	5702	0.00006495	1.001	6.922	0.06500	0.1445	$\bar{2}.8129$	$\bar{1}.6531$

TABLE VI.

Temp. = $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Cell constant = 0.3776 . Sp. conductivity of water = 1.30×10^{-6} mhos.

C.	R.	κ .	$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$.	Λ .	CA.	$1/\Lambda$.	Log [CA].	Log [CA ²].
0.125	1702	0.0002206	1.016	1.7928	0.2242	0.5577	$\bar{1}.3505$	$\bar{1}.6041$
0.09375	1984	0.0001890	1.012	2.040	0.1912	0.4903	$\bar{1}.2815$	$\bar{1}.5911$
0.07031	2247	0.0001668	1.008	2.392	0.1682	0.4980	$\bar{1}.2259$	$\bar{1}.6047$
0.0527	2564	0.0001459	1.007	2.786	0.1468	0.3590	$\bar{1}.1667$	$\bar{1}.6116$
0.03955	2860	0.0001307	1.006	3.324	0.1314	0.3009	$\bar{1}.1187$	$\bar{1}.6403$
0.02966	3193	0.0001169	1.004	3.956	0.1173	0.2527	$\bar{1}.0695$	$\bar{1}.6668$
0.02225	3605	0.0001034	1.002	4.656	0.1036	0.2147	$\bar{1}.0155$	$\bar{1}.6836$
0.01669	4016	0.00009273	1.002	5.566	0.09292	0.1797	$\bar{2}.9681$	$\bar{1}.7137$
0.01251	4418	0.00008416	1.001	6.732	0.08420	0.1486	$\bar{2}.9253$	$\bar{1}.7534$
0.00939	4929	0.00007529	1.000	8.022	0.07534	0.1247	$\bar{2}.8770$	$\bar{1}.7813$

TABLE VII.

Temperature coefficients of conductivity.

Temp. = 15°.

Temp. coeff. of conductivity for different temp. ranges.

C.	5°.	10°.	15°.	20°.	25°.
0·125	0·04602	0·05065	0·05360	0·05722	0·06061
0·09375	0·04817	0·05171	0·05509	0·05886	0·06039
0·07031	0·05182	0·05099	0·05564	0·05786	0·06189
0·0527	0·04875	0·05019	0·05456	0·06001	0·06082
0·03955	0·04776	0·05088	0·05656	0·05790	0·06139
0·02966	0·04646	0·05154	0·05582	0·05738	0·06223
0·02225	0·04923	0·05326	0·05723	0·06015	0·06218
0·01669	0·04825	0·05017	0·05672	0·05905	0·06175
0·01251	0·04545	0·05081	0·05822	0·06008	0·06270
0·00939	0·05163	0·05010	0·05744	0·06002	0·06200
Mean	0·04835	0·05103	0·05609	0·05885	0·06160

TABLE VIII.

Temperature coefficients of conductivity.

Temp = 20°.

Temp. coeff. of conductivity for different temp. ranges.

C.	5°.	10°.	15°.	20°.
0·125	0·04494	0·04666	0·04955	0·05226
0·09375	0·04455	0·04722	0·05031	0·05114
0·07031	*0·03984	0·04581	0·04753	0·05112
0·0527	0·04151	0·04619	0·05126	0·05133
0·03955	0·04358	0·04920	0·04945	0·05231
0·02966	0·04593	0·04907	0·04946	0·05367
0·02225	0·04595	0·04911	0·05117	0·05247
0·01669	0·04198	0·04912	0·05048	0·05247
0·01251	0·04574	0·05265	0·05290	0·05461
0·00939	*0·03860	0·04796	0·04992	0·05134
Mean	0·04427	0·04830	0·05020	0·05227

* These observations are rejected, due to accidental errors.

TABLE IX.

Temperature coefficients of conductivity.

Temp. = 25°.

C.	Temp. coeff. for different temp. ranges.			C.	Temp. coeff. for different temp. ranges,		
	5°.	10°.	15°.		5°.	10°.	15°.
0·125	0·03949	0·04233	0·04465	0·02966	0·04245	0·04169	0·04575
0·09375	0·04079	0·04350	0·04362	0·02225	0·04252	0·04374	0·04443
0·07031	0·04301	0·04286	0·04578	0·01669	0·04649	0·04523	0·04625
0·0527	0·04214	0·04649	0·04521	0·01251	*0·04846	0·04598	0·04685
0·03955	0·04502	0·04302	0·04532	0·00939	*0·04803	0·04659	0·04659
				Mean	0·04274	0·04414	0·04546

* Rejected due to accidental errors.

TABLE X.

Temperature coefficients for different ranges.

C.	At 30°.			C.	At 35°.		
	5°.	10°.	5°.		5°.	10°.	5°.
0·125	0·03770	0·03946	0·03466	0·02966	0·03375	0·03910	0·03803
0·09375	0·03835	0·03741	0·03059	0·02225	0·03708	0·03744	0·03188
0·07031	0·03517	0·03883	0·03613	0·01669	0·03565	0·03743	0·03328
0·0527	0·04199	0·03861	0·02911	0·01251	0·03501	0·03705	0·03326
0·03955	0·03350	0·03713	0·03490	0·00939	0·03641	0·03699	0·03178
				Mean	0·03646	0·03795	0·03336

TABLE XI.

Viscosities of HgCl₂ solutions at different temperatures. η , in absolute units.

C.	η_{15° .	η_{20° .	η_{25° .	η_{30° .	η_{35° .	η_{40° .
0.125	0.01190	0.01039	0.0091995	0.0081936	0.007367	0.006692
1.0969	2.0755	2.0165	3.9638	3.9135	3.8673	3.8255
0.09375	0.01184	0.01035	0.0091775	0.0081612	0.0073308	0.006665
2.9719	2.0734	2.0149	3.9628	3.9118	3.8652	3.8238
0.07031	0.01180	0.01031	0.0091417	0.0081356	0.0073028	0.006637
2.8471	2.0719	2.0132	3.9610	3.9104	3.8635	3.8220
0.0527	0.01179	0.010294	0.009119	0.008123	0.007298	0.006631
2.7218	2.0716	2.0125	3.9599	3.9098	3.8632	3.8216
0.03955	0.011765	0.01024	0.0091003	0.008110	0.007312	0.006625
2.5971	2.0707	2.0103	3.9590	3.9090	3.8640	3.8212
0.02966	0.011723	0.010243	0.0090893	0.008078	0.007298	0.006613
2.4722	2.0691	2.0104	3.9585	3.9073	3.8632	3.8204
0.02225	0.01172	0.01023	0.009072	0.008071	0.0072738	0.006600
2.3474	2.0690	2.0098	3.9577	3.9070	3.8617	3.8195
0.01669	0.01173	0.01025	0.009065	0.008071	0.007278	0.006597
2.2225	2.0693	2.0107	3.9573	3.9070	3.8620	3.8194
0.01251	0.011693	0.01023	0.009063	0.008072	0.0072656	0.006594
2.0972	2.0680	2.0098	3.9572	3.9070	3.8613	3.8192
0.00939	0.01169	0.010246	0.009052	0.008062	0.007263	0.006591
3.9727	2.0679	2.0105	3.9567	3.9064	3.8611	3.8190
Water	0.011683	0.010235	0.009043	0.0080626	0.007256	0.0065885
-	2.0678	2.0102	3.9563	3.9064	3.8606	3.8188

TABLE XII.

Temperature coefficients of viscosity.

Temp. = 15°.

C.	Temp. coeff. of viscosity for different temp. ranges				
	5°.	10°.	15°.	20°.	25°.
0·125	0·02538	0·02270	0·02076	0·01904	0·01751
0·09375	0·02517	0·02249	0·02071	0·01904	0·01748
0·07031	0·02525	0·02253	0·02070	0·01905	0·01750
0·0527	0·02538	0·02266	0·02073	0·01905	0·01750
0·03955	0·02592	0·02266	0·02071	0·01892	0·01748
0·02966	0·02524	0·02247	0·02073	0·01887	0·01744
0·02225	0·02543	0·02259	0·02075	0·01897	0·01748
0·01669	0·02523	0·02272	0·02080	0·01898	0·01750
0·01251	0·02502	0·02249	0·02065	0·01893	0·01745
0·00939	0·02471	0·02257	0·02069	0·01893	0·01745
Mean	0·02527	0·02259	0·02072	0·01898	0·01748

TABLE XIII.

Temperature coefficients of viscosity.

Temp. = 20°.

C.	Temp. coeff. of viscosity for different temp. ranges.			
	5°.	10°.	15°.	20°.
0·125	0·02292	0·02113	0·01939	0·01779
0·09375	0·02262	0·02114	0·01945	0·01780
0·07031	0·02267	0·02109	0·01945	0·01781
0·0527	0·02283	0·02109	0·01940	0·01779
0·03955	0·02226	0·02080	0·01906	0·01765
0·02966	0·02253	0·02113	0·01917	0·01772
0·02225	0·02263	0·02111	0·01927	0·01774
0·01669	0·02312	0·02126	0·01933	0·01782
0·01251	0·02281	0·02110	0·01932	0·01777
0·00939	0·02331	0·02131	0·01941	0·01783
Mean	0·02277	0·02112	0·019325	0·01777

TABLE XIV.

Temperature coefficients of viscosity.

Temp. = 25°.

C.	Temp. coeff. for ranges			C.	Temp. coeff. for ranges		
	5°.	10°.	15°.		5°.	10°.	15°.
0'125	0'02187	0'01992	0'01818	0'02966	0'02225	0'01971	0'01817
0'09375	0'02215	0'02012	0'01825	0'02225	0'02207	0'01983	0'01817
0'07031	0'02201	0'02011	0'01827	0'01669	0'02194	0'01972	0'01815
0'0527	0'02184	0'01997	0'01819	0'01251	0'02187	0'01984	0'01817
0'03955	0'02176	0'01965	0'01813	0'00939	0'02187	0'01976	0'01812
				Mean	0'02196	0'01986	0'01818

TABLE XV.

Temperature coefficients of viscosity.

C.	Temp. 30°.			C.	Temp. 35°.		
	Temp. coeff. for 5° range.				Temp. coeff. for 5° range.		
	5°.	10°.	5°.		5°.	10°.	5°.
0'125	0'02018	0'01832	0'01832	0'02966	0'01936	0'01813	0'01877
0'09375	0'02035	0'01833	0'01817	0'02225	0'01975	0'01823	0'01852
0'07031	0'02047	0'01842	0'01824	0'01669	0'01965	0'01827	0'01872
0'0527	0'02032	0'01837	0'01828	0'01251	0'01998	0'01827	0'01849
0'03955	0'01968	0'01837	0'01879	0'00939	0'01982	0'01825	0'01850
				Mean	0'01996	0'018296	0'01848

DISCUSSION.

The foregoing results show that within the limits of temperature investigated, Λ , the molecular conductivity of HgCl_2 in aqueous system, increases steadily with rise in T , the temperature (column 5, Tables I-VI). The Λ - T curves, corresponding to ten different dilutions shown in Fig. 1,

FIG. 1.

Influence of temp. on mol. conductivity.

show also that in all these cases the curve is inclined towards the Δ -axis and that this tendency becomes more pronounced as the dilution is increased. Data shown under column 3, in Tables I-VI indicate that HgCl_2 behaves as an extremely weak electrolyte, almost a non-electrolyte as is obvious from the exceedingly low order of the specific conductivities measured for even fairly concentrated solutions which are in close agreement with the results of Hampe (*loc. cit.*), Faraday (*loc. cit.*), Morse (*loc. cit.*), and others. The observed increase in the conductivity with the rise in temperature is partly explained

by our results that with the rise in temperature, the viscosity of the medium decreases; consequently, the mobility of the relevant ions would increase, which is in agreement with the findings of Kohlrausch (*loc. cit.*), Noyes, Melcher and Cooper (*loc. cit.*), Bousfield and Lowry (*loc. cit.*), Jones (*loc. cit.*) and others. Our result, that the departure from the linearity of the Λ - T curve increases with the dilution may in part be attributed to the increased hydrolysis of HgCl_2 with dilution. Ley (*loc. cit.*) has studied this in some detail. His results show that the hydrolysis of aqueous HgCl_2 is quite sensible even at 6° , its extent increases with dilution and temperature. The chief result of increased hydrolysis is to increase the hydrogen ion concentration and hence the corresponding conductivity. It is therefore to be anticipated that the departure from the linear relationship of the Λ - T curve, indicative of an extra rise in conductivity, may be produced as a result of increased hydrolysis. Our experimental results are in close accord with this deduction.

No quantitative information is available in the literature regarding the values for Λ_∞ , the molecular conductivity for HgCl_2 at infinite dilution at different temperatures to enable us to calculate the degrees of ionisation α , and also the dissociation constant, K , by the application of Ostwald's dilution law. An attempt has therefore, been made to evaluate Λ_∞ and K by the graphical method developed by Kraus and Bray (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 1315) and found to be utilisable for a surprisingly large number of electrolytes in both aqueous and non-aqueous solvents. The mass law expression as applied to weak electrolytes, undergoing binary dissociation gives

$$K = \frac{\Lambda^2 \cdot C}{(\Lambda_\infty - \Lambda)\Lambda_\infty} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

The equation (i) after rearranging reduces finally to

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_\infty} + \frac{1}{K \cdot \Lambda_\infty^2} (C\Lambda) \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

The plot of $C\Lambda$ (along abscissa) against $1/\Lambda$ (along the ordinate) gives a straight line; the intercept on the ordinate gives $1/\Lambda_\infty$ from which Λ_∞ and finally K can easily be computed; these curves, Kraus and Bray have designated as " $\Lambda_\infty - K$, plots". With a view to finding how far the equation

FIG. 2.

 $\Lambda_{\infty} - K$ plots.

(ii) holds in the case of HgCl_2 , these plots are shown in Fig. 2 after appropriate calculations from our data (Table I-VI). The curves, showing $\Lambda_{\infty} - K$ plots (Fig. 2, curves 1-6, at different temperatures), are all straight lines but give the intercepts on the negative side of the ordinate, to which, at present no physical meaning can be attached. It is, however, very significant that all these curves pass through a common point of intersection. For the sake of comparison Ley's data (*loc. cit.*) at 25° are also shown by a dotted curve [3 (b), Fig. 2]; his curve is slightly above ours on account of the fact that $1/\Lambda$ values of Ley were not, while our values are corrected for viscosity. This suggests that either, (a) the equation (ii), which holds for an electrolyte undergoing binary dissociation, may not adequately express the dissociation of mercuric chloride or (b), possibly, mercuric chloride does not belong to the type of electrolyte which undergoes simple binary dissociation considered in Kraus and Bray's procedure. Sherril (*loc. cit.*) calculated the ionisation constant K for

by E.M.F., and solubility data and partition of HgCl_2 between toluene and water, and toluene and mercuric nitrate solution. K for ternary dissociation was found to vary in the range 1×10^{-14} and 1.5×10^{-14} . The existence of the ions (HgCl') was established by Morse (*loc. cit.*) from the transport number measurements so that the ionisation of HgCl_2 , $\text{HgCl}_2 = \text{Hg}^{++} + 2\text{Cl}'$, takes place in stages :

The ionisation constants K_1 and K_2 for (a) and (b) were found to be 2.8×10^{-7} and 3.5×10^{-8} respectively. According to Luther, however, solution of HgCl_2 , saturated at 25° , contains the following constituents, expressed in moles per litre: $(\text{HgCl}_2) = 0.26$; $(\text{HgCl}') = 0.00015$; $(\text{H}') = 0.00033$; $(\text{Cl}') = 0.00048$; $(\text{Hg}'') = 10^{-8}$; $(\text{HgCl}'_4) = 5 \times 10^{-6}$. It is therefore, to be anticipated that the dissociation of HgCl_2 may not obey the simple binary dissociation law—a deduction in agreement with our results showing the departure in $\Delta_\infty - K$ plots as well as $\log(C\Delta) - \log(C\Delta^2)$ plots. The possible disturbing factors may now be considered: (i) The dissociation might proceed in stages: (a) $\text{HgCl}_2 = \text{HgCl}' + \text{Cl}'$; (b) $\text{HgCl}' = \text{Hg}'' + \text{Cl}'$; both the reactions (a) and (b) obey binary dissociation law and are of the same order; (ii) Causes leading to hydration or solvation, and (iii) hydrolysis leading to the formation of free HCl which dissociates into H^+ and Cl' . Discordant views prevail in regard to the mechanism of the hydrolysis of HgCl_2 . Ley (*loc. cit.*) suggested that the reaction proceeds as either, $2\text{HgCl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} = [\text{HgCl}_2]_2\text{O} + 2\text{H}' + 2\text{Cl}'$; or else, $\text{HgCl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{HgCl}(\text{OH}) + \text{H}' + \text{Cl}'$. Kahlenberg's results (*loc. cit.*) favour the first hypothesis. Fischer and Breiger (*Kolloid Z.*, 1910, 7, 196) suggested that HgCl_2 in aqueous solution is split up into HCl and a colloid. Thümmler (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1885, 223, 929) adduced evidence to show that aqueous HgCl_2 behaves as containing an acid $\text{H}_2(\text{HgOCl}_2)$ because of the peculiar hydrolytic changes.

It is interesting to consider the influence of temperature on the conductance of HgCl_2 (*cf.* Table VII-X). This is seen to be far higher than what obtains usually in the case of normal electrolytes. A survey of the data in the literature shows that the temperature coefficient of conductivity is about 1.6% for strong acids, 2.2% for binary electrolytes, and 2.5% for ternary electrolytes. Our result that this quantity for HgCl_2 varies in the range 3.8 to 6.2% suggests that either its ionisation is of a higher order involving a complex aggregate which gives ions, or else it is a typical weak electrolyte, it being known that the influence of temperature in increasing the conductivity is more marked in their case than with strong electrolytes, or what is more probable, both these factors might operate. The fact that the temperature coefficient of conductivity for aqueous HgCl_2 alters only slightly with dilution may be taken as evidence to show that HgCl_2 in aqueous solutions does not form hydrates, possibly because of its weak electrolytic nature. Jones (*Carnegie Inst. of Washington* 1907, Pb. 60) and collaborators have adduced very considerable evidence to show that there is no possibility of hydration taking place in the case of non-electrolytes, because of the comparative scarcity of the charged ions, which produce hydration due to the strong electrostatic forces of attraction between the charged ions and the dipolar water molecules.

It is interesting to point out that our data showing the effect of temperature on the conductivity of HgCl_2 , satisfy Kohlrausch's relation :

$$\Lambda_t = \Lambda_{t_0} [1 + a(t - t_0) + \beta(t - t_0)^2]$$

as is shown by the straight line curves (*cf.* Fig. 3, α , β plot) obtained by plotting

$$\frac{\Lambda_t - \Lambda_{t_0}}{\Lambda_{t_0} (t - t_0)}$$

on the ordinate, against $(t - t_0)$ on the abscissa, the intercept on the ordinate, and the slope of the curve give respectively the values of a and β , the coefficients appearing in the above equation. The coefficients are complicated functions of temperature, their values decreasing with rise in temperature. Our results showing the decrease of temperature coefficients of conductance with the corresponding fall in the values of coefficients a and β , with rise of temperature can be explained on the assumption that with rise in temperature the association of water becomes less (*cf.* Jones and West, *loc. cit.*, Ramsay and Shields, *loc. cit.*) and thus brings about the lowering in the ionising power of the solvent medium (*cf.* Dutoit and Aston). The fact that the dissociation decreases

with rise of temperature is also in agreement with the conclusions that can be drawn from the results of Vonwiller (*loc. cit.*) showing a decrease in the dielectric constant of water with rise of temperature, and the Thomson-Nernst's rule (*Phil. Mag.*, 1893, 36, 313; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 13, 535; *cf.* Kraus and Fuoss, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 21; 1933, 55, 476, 1019) connecting the dissociating power of a solvent with its dielectric constant. That the temperature coefficients of conductivity decrease with rise of temperature is in harmony with the views of Bousfield and Lowry (*loc. cit.*) on other independent grounds.

FIG. 4.

Influence of conc. on viscosity at diff. temp.

Our results on the viscosities of aqueous HgCl_2 for different concentrations and at different temperatures (*cf.* Table XI) show that the viscosity coefficient at any temperature increases with the concentration, especially in fairly strong solutions; in very dilute solutions difficulties arise owing to the fact that the viscosity of the solution varies from that of the pure solvent (water), to an extent which comes within the range of the experimental error. The above variations of viscosity with concentration and temperature can be adequately expressed by the expressions, $\log \eta = kC$ and $\log \eta = \frac{B}{T} - A$, where C is the volume concentration in moles per litre, T , the absolute temperature, k , B , and A being constants as is shown by

straight line curves of $\log \eta$ against C (cf. curves 1-6 in Fig. 4) and against $\frac{1}{T}$ (curves 1-10 in Fig. 5) (cf. Berl and Umstätter and Karrer, *loc. cit.*)

FIG. 5.
Influence of temp. on viscosity for diff. conc.

Our results on the temperature coefficients of viscosity of aqueous HgCl_2 (cf. Tables XII-XV) at different temperature ranges, show that the temperature coefficient, $\frac{\eta_t - \eta_{t_0}}{\eta_{t_0}(t - t_0)}$ increases (algebraically) with rise in temperature.

It is, however, interesting to point out that the temperature coefficients of viscosity of HgCl_2 solutions are almost equal to those of the pure solvent, water. It is also seen that the temperature coefficient of viscosity of the solvent (water) remains unaltered despite the varying concentration of HgCl_2 present in the system. Our data showing the effect of temperature on the viscosity of aqueous HgCl_2 satisfy the relation (cf. Bousfield and Lowry, *loc. cit.*), $\eta_t = \eta_{t_0} [1 + \alpha(t - t_0) + \beta(t - t_0)^2]$ as is seen from the straight

line graphs obtained by plotting $\frac{\eta_t - \eta_{t_0}}{\eta_{t_0}(t - t_0)}$ on the ordinate against $(t - t_0)$ on the abscissa (*cf.* curves 1-4, α , β plots in Fig. 6). The values of the coefficients α and β , the former being negative and the latter positive,

FIG. 6.

appearing in the above equation, have been graphically evaluated. The intercept on the ordinate and the slope of the curve give respectively the values of α and β .

ELECTROCHEMISTRY SECTION,
CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
BENARÉS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
BENARÉS.

Received June 12, 1940.

